

PHRASEOLOGICAL PREPOSITION AS A STRUCTURAL COMPONENT OF PHRASEOLOGISMS-UNION

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ABSTRACT

In this article structural features of phraseological prepositions and structural component of phraseologisms-union will be discussed broadly with clear illustrations which is one of the questionable and tough side of English language.

Phraseology could be portrayed as gallery, where representations of the nation's cultural customs are collected. Under this perspective, this field of language is not only the most colorful, but also probably the most egalitarian area of vocabulary and it drowns its resources mostly from the very depths of popular speech. Moreover, together with the study of synonyms and antonyms, phraseology represents one of the most expressive disciplines within linguistics. It is precisely due to its richness of expressions and to its heterogeneity that it seems difficult to identify which are the borders of phraseology. Delimiting the object of study of phraseology and finding a uniformed classification system seems to be a difficult task. In fact, the same terminological diversity that linguists have used to refer both to the generic discipline and to the elements it studies highlights its instability. Despite the increasing amount

of research within phraseology in the past fifty years, and the consequent improvement regarding the delimitation of the units that constitute its object of study, there seems to be still a great diversity of criteria. This hinders the consolidation of a systematic and scientific study of this topic .

We maintain a very productive idea flashed out by the linguist and consisting in that phraseological meaning cannot be realized without the existence of definite structures, i.e. it is impossible to study the features of phraseological units without knowledge of their structure. There are, as far as his scheme goes, seven main structural types of phraseological units in the English language. They are as follows:

1. Unitop phraseological units (the term was introduced by A.I. Smirnitsky consisting of one notional and one functional lexeme, or one notional and two

or three functional lexemes. By functional lexemes one should consider lexemes which do not function as independent members of the sentence and serve for word connection in the sentence (prepositions, conjunctions), and also for characterization of the categories of number, definiteness or indefiniteness of nouns (or articles).

2. Phraseological units with the structure of subordinate or coordinate combination of words (to have a finger in every pie „to be involved in every plan; high and mighty” the powerful minority).

3. Phraseological units with the partially predicative structure (i.e. lexeme + subordinate clause): ships that pass in the night momentary encounters).

4. Phraseological units with the structure of subordinate clause (when pigs fly (colloq.) never);

5. Phraseological units of nominative-communicative class, i.e. verbal constructions with the structure of a word combination with a verb in the form of infinitive and the structure of a sentence with a verb in the passive voice (break the ice “C to make a beginning > the ice is broken the beginning is made).

6. Phraseological units with the structure of a simple or complex sentence (A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush. Better an egg today than a hen tomorrow;

Do you see any green in my eye? Do you really think me to be so naive? Tell it to the marines! Nonsense!).

Phraseologisms-unions, which include phraseological prepositions, began to form in the 19th century, in the 21st century their rapid formation and development is taking place. Phraseological prepositions are part of phraseological conjunctions not by themselves, but as part of prepositional

constructions that retain functional case meanings, for example: despite the fact that, judging by how, due to the fact that, insofar as, in the name of the fact that, due to the fact that.

Phraseologisms-unions with a structural component - a phraseological preposition are formed according to the model "Analogue of a combination of words". In their structure, they contain from three (if) to five (due to the fact that) components that have a contact arrangement. In our card file there are 130 such language units, which is 40% of the collected material. Phraseologisms-unions of this structural association have one common subordinate subcategorical meaning, but different group semes: time, cause, concession, condition, goal, consequence, comparison, attachment. A phraseological preposition, being a component of a phraseological unit-union, retains that part of the grammatical meaning that comes from the prepositional form. In phraseological prepositions, the functional meaning of the prepositional case form turns into a categorical one.

For example, the component is a phraseological preposition during (what) into the semantic structure of a phraseologism-union, while it introduces the seme "an expression of temporary relations, when something happens at one of the moments or throughout any action, state". The component is a lexical conjunction as to the seme 'precisely', which is actualized in its first meaning. Component - the pronoun then - this 'indication'. Phraseologism-union while attaches the subordinate part of the sentence with the meaning 'indication of the accuracy of the action of the subordinate part at one of the moments or

throughout the duration of the main sentence'. "While Pushkin, who had never been abroad, was in Mikhailovskaya exile, the novice diplomat A. Gorchakov served in Paris". The component is a phraseological preposition from the day (what) into the semantic structure of a phraseological unit-union from the day it introduces a "short period of time" to the seme. The component is the lexical conjunction as to the seme 'precisely', which is actualized in its first meaning. Component - the pronoun of that - this 'indication'. Phraseologism-union from the day it "indicates the accuracy of the beginning of the action of the main part of the sentence after a short interval from the beginning of the action of the subordinate part". "From the day Pierre, leaving the Rostovs and remembering Natasha's grateful look, looked at the comet standing in the sky, and felt that something new had opened up for him, the question of the futility and madness of everything earthly, which had always tormented him, ceased to present itself to him. Phraseological prepositions, which are a structural component of phraseological units-unions, shaping the relationship of cause, introduce semes of consequence, reason, reason into their meanings (as a sign that, based on the fact that, for (that) reason that, for (that) occasion that, in by virtue of the fact that, under the guise of the fact that, as a result of the fact that, on the basis of that), conditions (on the occasion of the fact that, due to the fact that, judging by the fact that, in the presence of the fact that), goals (based on what), an object (in part because). For example, a phraseological preposition about (what) introduces into the meaning of a phraseological unit-union about the

fact that this is "an indication of the content, the subject of speech, thoughts, feelings". The component is a lexical union which, in the first meaning, actualizes the seme 'additional basis'. Component - the pronoun of that - this 'indication'. Phraseologism-union about the fact that it attaches the subordinate part of the sentence and 'indicates an additional basis for the descriptive transmission of speech, the thoughts of the person referred to in the main part'. "At the last meeting of the balance commission, there was an alarm about the fact that the state owes Mayak a lot of money for the state defense order ..."

. Phraseological preposition in case (of which) introduces into the meaning of phraseological units-unions in (that, those) case (s) if, in (separate, that, those) case (s) when, in the event that this is an indication of the circumstances that should trigger certain actions. "If I'm late, don't wait for me, start the rehearsal" (From colloquial speech). Phraseologism-union in case it attaches the subordinate part of the sentence with the meaning of the real condition. Thus, phraseological prepositions introduce their subcategorical, group, subgroup and individual semes into phraseological units. The connection between the phraseological unit-union and the phraseological preposition testifies to the development of analyticism in the expression of syntactic relations, the desire of a modern person to clearly, logically correctly express a thought. Phraseologisms-unions with a structural component - a phraseological preposition - are mainly used in book literary speech, they are characterized by low frequency.

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